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The Remarkable Journey of Vinod Kumar Goenka

Vinodgoenka · Follow

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Summary of his achievements; in and outside the boardroom

Vinod Kumar Goenka: Early Life

Vinod Kumar Goenka, a well-known personality in the India Real Estate Industry was born in Kolkata in 1959. Soon after when he turned 6, he moved to Mumbai with his family. He started his early schooling at Green Lawns High School and then switched to Jamnabai Narsee School. He finally completed his schooling at Campion School in Fort, Mumbai. Over the years of his education and the different schools he attended, he continued to excel both in sports and academics.

Vinod Kumar Goenka: Excelling in Sports and Academics

In addition to being good in his academics, he also showed equal talent and success in sports. Over the years he also represented his school and state in various sporting competitions and won multiple accolades.

Vinod Kumar Goenka started his journey in sports at the young age of 12 when he was studying at Jamnabai Narsee School. He mainly focussed on sprinting and the long jump and showed enough promise and dedication to excel. He achieved significant recognition in the under 16 category sprinting 100 metres in 11.5 seconds, 200 metres in 23.4 seconds and completing a long jump with 6.31 metres.

While he continued to focus on his education and academics, he also continued to bring laurels to his schools during sporting events. He represented Champion School after moving in the 8th grade. He also participated in well-known city events like the Interschool Athletics Championship, YMCA Competitions, Cadbury's Athletic Championship, Bombay Suburban Athletic meet and Greater Bombay Amateur Athletic Association to name a few. His talents also took him beyond the city limits when he represented Mumbai in the Maharashtra State Amateur Athletic Association Meet and later as an important team member of the state's team in the National Games.

Unfortunately, at the age of 16 when Vinod Kumar Goenka was preparing for the Asian Games, he suffered a hamstring injury which led him to drop out and end his career in professional sports.

However, that did not deter him. He continues to give sports immense importance in his life and is still a very active part of his daily schedule even today. He gives a lot of importance to his physical fitness and health. He currently plays squash regularly to maintain his physical fitness. He also gives equal importance to his diet and regularly weightlifting showing that his conscious self is still connected to sports one way or the other.

Vinod Kumar Goenka: Excelling in Entrepreneurship

Vinod Kumar Goenka is a well-known figure in the Indian Real Estate Industry and currently manages DB Realty Ltd as a Managing Director and Chairman, a Mumbai-based real estate and hospitality development firm. With a career spanning more than 35 years, he has made his mark in the industry as a successful business tycoon with successful projects in the commercial, residential and hospitality sectors. His current portfolio comprises more than 20 million square feet of development and he continues to showcase his talents and expertise in his ongoing projects. He started working at the young age of 19 by joining his father's business in the 1980s. Under his guided leadership and vision, the company grew exponentially helping him amass assets worth 1.1 billion dollars.

One of the major milestones for the company was being listed on both the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) and National Stock Exchange (NSE) in 2010. Even today, under his leadership and vision, the company continues to grow at a steady pace. As the Chairman and Managing Director, he sets the future direction of the company, leads corporate strategy formulation, establishes goals and manages performance for his key executives and employees. It is evident from his commitment and dedication that he envisions taking DB Realty to further heights.

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Vinod Goenka, the Chairman and Managing Director of DB Realty, stands as a luminary. Visit : https://www.dbrealty.co.in/vinod_goenka.php

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- Led Your Transactions implementation for JavaScript front-end framework to showcase consumer transactions and reduce call center costs by \$25 Million
- Recovered Saudi Arabia checkout failure impacting 4000+ customers due to incorrect GET form redirection

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```

```
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  console.log(1)  
  resolve(2)  
})
```

```
promise1.then(res => {  
  console.log(res)  
})
```

```
console.log('end');
```

start

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